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Stress and immune response to centrifugal pumping of *Salmo salar* in an industrial recirculating aquaculture system: A case study

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ABSTRACT

Salmo salar, the most economically important salmonid, is commonly reared in recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) during its land-based production phases. Although pumps are frequently employed to transfer fish in RAS, their impact on fish is poorly understood. This study is the first to follow a transfer performed through centrifugal pumping in a commercial RAS, investigating its effect on the stress and immune status of fish, and their ability to recover over a week. This was assessed through the analysis of physiological, biochemical and molecular indicators of stress responses and inflammation, in plasma and relevant organs. The primary and secondary stress responses were triggered, as indicated by the alterations in biochemical parameters. Cortisol levels were lower than expected throughout the case study, indicating a possible exhaustion, or decreased sensitivity, of the hypothalamus-pituitary-interrenal (HPI) axis. In the gills and head kidney, all genes displayed significant alterations. The results indicate that, in this specific industry-based case, centrifugal pumping elicited a stress response in *S. salar* smolt, but this stress did not appear to be maladaptive, as the fish were able to maintain homeostasis. This study, having been performed in industrial settings, provides results of greater representativeness of real-life scenarios compared to laboratory experiments or simulations. Further research following the stress and immune status of *S. salar* in industrial settings throughout the production cycle is required to investigate whether rearing conditions in commercial RAS do indeed alter the HPI axis responsiveness and the immune-endocrine interactions.

1. Introduction

Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.) is the most produced salmonid species by the aquaculture industry, representing over 70 % of total salmonid production and 30 % of the total fish production from the marine aquaculture industry, equalling over 2.7 million metric tonnes per year [1,2]. The farming of this species is dominated by five countries, with Norway, Chile, Canada, the United Kingdom and the Faroe Islands accounting for over 90 % of the total global production [1,3]. *S. salar* is therefore one of the most economically important fish, and an

increasing number of producing companies are implementing recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) for the land-based phases of salmonid production [4,5].

These systems, characterised by major water reutilisation rates (>90 %) and a variety of filtration mechanisms (e.g. mechanical and biological), sterilisation and oxygenation systems, allow for the rearing of high densities of aquatic organisms in settings virtually isolated from the surrounding environment [6,7]. Therefore, RAS allow for increased control over water quality, enhanced fish welfare and significantly reduced environmental impact of the aquaculture facility [6,8,9]. In

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RAS, like in most aquaculture practices, fish are subjected to handling, transportation, and are susceptible to being transferred from a tank to a truck, or a boat, as part of transport to sea or to slaughtering facilities, or from one tank to another in order to reduce density. The use of pumps to this end is common practice [10]. Although highly frequent and often inevitable, these transfers are inherently stressful events, and are most often preceded by a slight crowding episode to facilitate the transfer process [11,12].

In fish, the primary stress response is mediated by the activation of the hypothalamus-pituitary-interrenal (HPI) axis, characterised by a rise in cortisol levels, and the brain-sympathetic-chromaffin (BSC) axis characterised by the release of catecholamines [13]. When the hypothalamus initiates the activation of sympathetic fibres, chromaffin cells in the head kidney release catecholamines which, in turn, lead to an increase in the availability of energetic resources to aid in the “fight or flight” response. In addition, the activation of the HPI axis induces the release of corticotropin releasing factor (CRF) from the preoptic area in the brain. In the pituitary gland, CRF starts a process resulting in the synthesis of adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) which prompts the production and release of cortisol into the bloodstream [13,14]. This triggers the secondary response, which encompasses a variety of physiological and metabolic adaptations related to allostasis (e.g. increase in circulating glucose and lactate; [15]), rise of inflammatory mediators [16]. Significant alterations in these pathways might have cascading effects, impacting the immune capacity of the fish, its disease resistance, reproduction, growth, and overall performance [13]. Furthermore, it has been reported that stress induces immunodepression and fragilizes living organisms, and that subsequent mild stressors following a major stressing event are more likely to result in mortalities [17,18]. It is clear that exposure to stress in cultured fishes might have strong repercussions on the sustainability and profitability of the aquaculture sector by increasing susceptibility to disease and causing mortality events. Therefore, it is of greatest interest to precisely understand how common commercial practices affect the overall stress and welfare status of fishes in order to develop and implement mitigation techniques, both from an economic and an ethical point of view.

According to previously published research, the practice of transferring fish elicits the activation of the stress response in fishes, with significant intensity differences between techniques. Indeed, it has been reported that vacuum pumping is more stressful than other loading techniques, such as netting, and might significantly extend the recovery period [19,20] in addition to significantly decreasing product quality by reducing the *rigor mortis* onset time [21]. Previous research focusing on the effects of pumping in fish has investigated mainly biochemical parameters in the plasma [19,20,22], behaviour [23], muscle pH [24], survival [25], or onset time of *rigor mortis* [21,26] in laboratory conditions. However, to the best of the authors knowledge, no study has focused on the impact of fish centrifugal pumping on biochemical parameters and molecular endpoints in *S. salar* smolt directly in a commercial RAS setting. While conducting this type of investigation in commercial settings, following routine operations without any sort of intervention from the researchers, does not allow for tank replicates, it provides insightful information on what occurs in a real-life scenario and enhances the applicability of the results. Previously conducted RAS-based studies mostly focused on the response of mucosal surfaces (i.e. mainly gills and skin) to changes in the system [27].

Thus, the present case study is the first to examine the effect that a standardised transfer operation (i.e. with density reduction as primary objective) might have on the general stress, welfare, and immune status of *S. salar* in an industrial RAS, and the capacity of the fish to recover from the event. To this end common physiological indicators of the primary and secondary stress response (i.e. circulating cortisol and glucose levels, in the plasma), liver activity and damage (i.e. aspartate aminotransferase, AST; alanine transaminase, ALT), and immune and inflammatory regulation (adenosine deaminase, ADA) were researched. In addition, the relative abundance of genes relevant to the general

stress response (i.e. glucocorticoid receptor 1, *gr1*; glucocorticoid receptor 2, *gr2*; mineralocorticoid receptor, *mr*; corticotropin releasing factor, *crf*), homeostasis (i.e. heat shock protein 70, *hsp70*), and pro-inflammatory cytokines (i.e. tumour necrosis factor alpha, *tnfa*; interleukin 1 beta; *il1β*) were investigated in head kidney and gills. Furthermore, the *star* (steroidogenic acute regulatory) protein-coding gene was assessed in the head kidney, and mucin-coding genes (i.e. *muc2* and *muc18*) were analysed in the gills. Gills were also selected for the present case study as, being a highly sensitive mucosal surface in direct contact with the surrounding environments, they are known to be influenced by both acute and chronic stressors, and be involved in maintaining homeostasis [11,28]. On the other hand, the head kidney was investigated given their involvement in the regulation of both primary and secondary stress responses, as well as in neuro-immuno-endocrine signalling pathways [16,29]. Thus, the selected endpoints reflect, to some extent, the response of both the peripheral and central systems.

The hypotheses were two-fold. Firstly, it was expected that the transfer from one tank to another through pumping would trigger the stress response in *S. salar*, (i.e. reflected by an almost immediate rise in plasmatic cortisol levels, followed by an increase in glucose, and variations both in biochemical parameters and in the expression of relevant genes) in an organ-specific manner, indicating potential compensatory mechanisms between the peripheral and central systems. Secondly, it was hypothesised that all investigated parameters would return to control levels shortly after the start of the recovery period (up to 7 days post stress).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sampling

A total of 40 *S. salar* smolt (64.7 ± 18 g total weight, 18.7 ± 1.5 cm total length) were sampled from an industrial RAS farm at five different time points (A-E; Fig. 1). The sampling took place around a standardised pumping episode destined to transfer fish from one tank (X, 50 m³) to another (Y, 35 m³) in the same facility to reduce density and prevent overcrowding stress. Both tanks were round-shaped and presented a water retention time of 45 min. In both cases, the biological filtration for the circulating water was performed by fixed-bed biofilters. The sampling points were distributed over time as follows:

- A 48 h before the start of the transfer, in tank X. Control or pre-treatment group.
- B During transfer, in tank X.
- C 1 h after the transfer, in tank Y (1hps).
- D 24 h after the transfer, in tank Y (24hps).
- E 7 days after the transfer, in tank Y (7dps).

No specific indications were given to the farm operators as to how to perform the transfer, ensuring that the event was not influenced by the sampling, and that the results would reflect as much as possible a real-life, commercial scenario [25]. The fish were subjected to a 24 h light photoperiod throughout the land-based production phase and were food-deprived 24 h prior to the beginning of the transport. Directly before the transfer, the water level in tank X was slightly lowered, resulting in a slight crowding of the fish, with density increasing from 95.97 kg/m³ to 100 kg/m³. The transfer was performed through centrifugal pumping, during which fish were transported via a plastic hose (65m × 110 mm), at a speed of ca. 1 m/s (approximately 1 min from tank to tank). The water temperature in tank X did not differ greatly from that in tank Y, with 8.2 and 8.5 °C, respectively. On the other hand, the initial density (in tank X) was estimated at 95.97 kg/m³, whereas the final density (in the receiving tank, Y) was estimated at 51,3 kg/m³. The entire transfer process lasted approximately 2 h.

Eight fish were randomly collected from the industrial tanks and

Experimental conditions

Fig. 1. Description of the sampling procedure during the transfer of *Salmo salar* smolts through centrifugal pumping to reduce density (N = 40, no tank replicates; hps = hours post stress, dps = days post stress) Letters A-E in the diagram indicate sampling points. Source: Biorender.

immediately anaesthetised by immersion in 300 mg/L of MS-222 (Finquel, MSD Animal Health) buffered with 600 mg/L of sodium bicarbonate. Once the fish had reached stage 3 of anaesthesia (*i.e.* surgical), they were carefully removed from the anaesthesia tank, checked for injuries, malformations, and signs of disease, weighed, and measured. Once the fish was deemed healthy by the local fish biologist (*i.e.* absence of evident injuries and pathologies), blood was extracted using heparinised syringes equipped with 24G needles. The obtained blood was placed in individual Eppendorf tubes and stored at 4 °C under dark conditions until further processing. Subsequently, the fish were euthanised by re-immersion in the anaesthesia tank until stage 4 was attained (*i.e.* medullary collapse), and death was confirmed with a sharp cut through the spine. Once the individual was dead, the head kidney and gills were extracted, immediately stored individually in RNA Later® (Ambion) and subsequently stored at -80 °C until further processing and analysis. A summary of all analysed endpoints in each matrix is available (Suppl. 2).

2.2. Plasma extraction and biochemical endpoints

The collected blood samples were centrifuged at 2000 g over a 10-

min period in a cooling centrifuge maintaining the temperature at 4 °C in order to obtain plasma for subsequent biochemical analyses. Cortisol levels were determined with an automated analyser (Immulate 1000, Siemens Health Diagnostics) using a commercial immunoassay (LKC01, Siemens Health Diagnostics). Glucose levels were also analysed with an automated analyser (Olympus Diagnostics) following the manufacturer's recommendations. ADA activity was determined with commercially available kits (Adenosine Deaminase assay kit, Diazyme Laboratories, Poway, CA, USA) as per the provider's instructions. AST and ALT were measured in the plasma of fish using commercial kits (Olympus Systems Reagents; Olympus life and Material Science Europe GmbH, Hamburg, Germany). All automated assays were previously validated for fish [30].

2.3. RNA extraction, complementary DNA synthesis and real-time quantitative Polymerase chain reaction

A total of 20 mg of each organ samples was placed in RLT lysis buffer (Qiagen GmbH, Germany) homogenised with the TissueLyser II (Qiagen) at 30Hz for 4 min on each side to ensure an equal degree of mixing throughout the samples. RNA was then extracted using the RNeasy Mini

Kit following the manufacturer's directions, with minor modifications in the centrifugation steps, increasing the centrifuge's speed to 9400 g. Complementary DNA (cDNA) was synthesised by reverse transcription using the commercially available kit LunaScript™ RT SuperMix Kit (NEB E3010L, New England BioLabs Inc, USA) following the manufacturer's recommendations. The efficiency of all selected primers (Suppl.1) was tested through RT-qPCR of serial dilutions of pooled cDNA [31] to ensure that all efficiencies were in the range of 90–110 %. RT-qPCRs were performed using 384-well plates, each containing a final volume of 5 μ L, comprising 2.5 μ L of Universal SYBR® Green Supermix (Bio-Rad, USA), 250 nM of the corresponding primer pair (forward and reverse) and 1 μ L of cDNA at the previously determined optimal dilution. The qPCR protocol, ran through the BIO-RADCFX384 Real-Time PCR Detection System (Bio-Rad), was the following: 95 °C for 3 min, and a cycle of 10 s at 95 °C and 30 s at 60 °C repeated 40 times.

2.4. Data analysis

The pre-selected reference genes (Suppl. 1) were tested for their stability throughout the samples using the GENorm algorithm already incorporated into the Bio-Rad CFX Maestro Software (Bio-Rad), with the results indicating organ specific combinations of the most suitable reference genes for the present case study (Gills: *18S* and *β actin*; Head kidney: *18S* and *β actin*). The gene expression of the target genes was then calculated relative to that of these reference genes following the Bio-Rad CFX Maestro User Guide's indications. All collected data were tested for normality and homoscedasticity, and data that met the assumptions were analysed with parametric one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post-hoc tests. On the other hand, data that did not meet the assumptions were treated with the non-parametric equivalents, namely, Kruskal-Wallis tests, and False Discovery Rate tests. All data were analysed using GraphPad Prism 8. Moreover, the sampling effect was tested to evaluate the impact of the absence of tank replicates (data not shown), and the results indicated no significant effect of sampling.

3. Results

3.1. Plasma biochemistry

The analyses conducted indicate significant differences in the plas-matic biochemical profiles of *S. salar* (Fig. 2). The determined values of circulating cortisol ranged between 0.05 and 15 ng/ml. A significant increase in cortisol levels was observed at sampling points B and C, with a subsequent significant decrease afterwards. Glucose levels in *S. salar* plasma displayed a significant increase from point B to C followed by a significant decrease after sampling point E. The levels of plasmatic AST followed a significant increase towards point C, followed by a decrease until reaching control levels in the subsequent sampling points. ALT levels in plasma displayed a slight but non-significant increase during pumping, but levels significantly decreased at point D and E relative to the control. The determined ADA levels in plasma displayed a significant increase at point B, with a slight, non-significant decrease at point C. These levels returned to control values at point D, with a subsequent significant increase at point E.

3.2. Gene expression

In the head kidney (Fig. 3), *gr1* was significantly downregulated in all sampling points compared to the control (point A), with mRNA levels of this gene stabilising at point C, and subsequently decreasing significantly at point E. In addition, the expression of *crf*, *gr2* and *hps70*, displayed decreasing trends, with significant downregulations only at point E. However, the results indicate a significant decrease in mRNA abundance of *tnfa* directly after the stress started (point A), remaining stable up to 24hps, and further decreasing at point E. On the other hand, *mr* was not affected in the head kidney in the present case study. Similarly, the relative abundance of *il1 β* in this organ was not significantly affected during the pumping event, although a significant reduction was observed in point E compared to all other sampling points. Likewise, the expression of *star* did not result significantly altered during the pumping process, but a significant downregulation was observed in point E compared to control values.

Fig. 2. Biochemical parameters investigated in *Salmo salar* plasma during a centrifugal pumping episode in a commercial recirculated aquaculture system (RAS). Cortisol; glucose; AST: aspartate aminotransferase; ALT: alanine transaminase; ADA: adenosine deaminase. A: 48 h before exposure; B: during transfer; C: 1hps; D: 24hps; E: 7dps. Different letters above columns indicate significant differences between sampling points ($P < 0.05$; $N = 40$).

Fig. 3. Relative gene expression analysed in head kidney of *Salmo salar* during a centrifugal pumping episode in a commercial recirculated aquaculture system (RAS). A: 48 h before exposure; B: during transfer; C: 1hps; D: 24hps; E: 7dps. Different letters above columns indicate significant differences between sampling points ($P < 0.05$; $N = 40$). *gr1*: glucocorticoid receptor 1; *gr2*: glucocorticoid receptor 2; *mr*: mineralocorticoid receptor; *crf*: corticotropin releasing factor; *hsp70*: heat shock protein 70; *star*: steroidogenic acute regulatory protein; *il1β*: interleukin 1 beta; *tnfa*: tumor necrosis factor alpha.

In the gills of *S. salar* (Fig. 4) all studied genes exhibited a significant increase in abundance at point B compared to the control, with the exception of *mr* which displayed a significant upregulation only at point C. In no case was there any significant differences in mRNA abundance of the studied genes between points B, C and D, and in all cases the expression of genes observed at point E was comparable to that measured at point A, with no statistical differences arising.

4. Discussion

Few studies have been carried out in industrial salmon facilities, following the exact same procedures used for commercial fishes. Therefore, the present case study is not a laboratory or pilot experiment closely simulating the farm situation, but a direct measurement during an actual salmon production process. This provides more accurate data on the effects of stress linked to industrial husbandry practices during commercial fish production.

4.1. Physiological indicators in plasma

The observed increase in plasma cortisol levels during the stress and 1hps indicates the triggering of the primary stress response [13] as expected after an acute stress, corroborating previous findings in salmonids (for instance, see Ref. [32]). Although previous research conducted

on the direct impact of pumping on *S. salar* has reported contradictory results, with some describing no significant changes in plasma cortisol levels [19,22–24], there is evidence that this practice might significantly increase circulating cortisol levels [25]. However, the aforementioned studies have focused on the impact of vacuum pumping and turbine pumping, while the transfer event hereby investigated was performed through centrifugal pumping. Thus, differences between the present results and past studies might also be attributed to these methodology-related variations, the experimental vs. industrial environment, as well as the pre-stress conditions. Furthermore, differences between reported tendencies in plasma cortisol fluctuations in past research might arise from dissimilarities in pumping design (e.g. hose dimensions, velocity). Other possible explanations for the disagreements between studies regarding cortisol behaviour are differences in analytical methods and sampling techniques (including time of day of sampling).

As expected, these measurements returned to control levels by sampling point D (i.e. less than 24hps). This is in accordance with previously published results indicating a return to basal cortisol levels in the plasma of *S. salar* 6 h after pumping [25]. Nonetheless, it is noteworthy that, although significantly different, the values of plasma cortisol amongst all groups are situated between 0.05 and 15 ng/mL, even in the groups B and C, which display the highest values. In contrast, it has been reported that basal levels of circulating cortisol for *S. salar* smolt

Fig. 4. Relative gene expression analysed in gills of *Salmo salar* during a centrifugal pumping episode in a commercial recirculated aquaculture system (RAS). A: 48 h before exposure; B: during transfer; C: 1hps; D: 24hps; E: 7dps. Different letters above columns indicate significant differences between sampling points ($P < 0.05$; $N = 40$). *gr1*: glucocorticoid receptor 1; *gr2*: glucocorticoid receptor 2; *mr*: mineralocorticoid receptor; *muc2*: mucin 2; *muc18*: mucin 18; *crf*: corticotropin releasing factor; *tnfa*: tumor necrosis factor alpha; *il1β*: interleukin 1 beta; *hsp70*: heat shock protein 70.

oscillate around 4 ng/mL, with some studies indicating basal cortisol values of up to 30 ng/mL, and that, following a challenge with stressors similar to the one studied here, these might rise to considerably higher levels than those observed in the present case study [33–35]. For instance Ref. [36], reported that *S. salar* smolts subjected to handling displayed cortisol levels rising from a basal levels of around 3.8 ng/mL to around 25.8 3hps, recovering basal values 24hps. Although differences in analytical methods might explain, to some extent, the considerable differences in circulating cortisol levels detected, the technique hereby employed has been previously validated for salmonids [37], and it is, thus, highly unlikely that such differences arise solely from the quantification method. Instead, the low values shown by the present results may indicate that the HPI axis has not been greatly activated or that the HPI axis has been somehow desensitised due to feedback mechanisms, given that, in many fish species, levels equal to, or below 10 ng/mL may be considered basal levels [38–40]. Therefore, a reasonable explanation is the possibility that these fish show a lower HPI-axis responsiveness due to previous repeated and prolonged exposure to stressors common in RAS, such as overcrowding, noise, or constant light [41,42], thus possibly either exhausting the axis, or reducing its ability to show a more powerful cortisol release response. Indeed, it has been reported that, RAS, being such complex system, have components that both promote, and have deleterious impacts on, fish health and welfare [27]. Similar patterns of inhibited stress axes as a

consequence of chronic exposure to stress have been described in birds, with both decreased basal cortisol levels and lower increases in this parameter following novel acute stressors [43]. Similarly, in humans exposed to chronic stress and/or experiencing PTSD, lower cortisol levels and a hindered responsiveness of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA; analogous to the HPI axis in fish) axis have been reported [44]. Nonetheless, the present findings are suggestive, rather than definitive, providing preliminary insights on the matter. Indeed, the obtained results are not sufficient to conclusively support this hypothesis, and additional research and data are needed to confidently ascertain whether this mechanism also takes place in fish.

The observed initial decrease in plasmatic glucose levels agrees with published literature describing a significant decrease in circulating glucose levels shortly after a crowding event, followed by a significant increase in this parameter, both relative to control values [45], with the latter indicating the successful triggering of the secondary stress response. In addition, a return to basal levels of plasmatic glucose after a stress-induced increase has been reported to take over 24 h [18], further agreeing with the present results. This is also in accordance with the low but significant increase in cortisol, which would induce the catabolic increase of plasmatic glucose levels [13].

Past studies investigating liver damage resulting from pumping in fish have reported species-specific variations in certain indicators (e.g. ALT, AST). Xu et al. [46] described significant differences in the

fluctuations of biochemical parameters in the serum of various cyprinid fishes, including these liver health biomarkers, with some species displaying significant increases in circulating levels of ALT and AST following pumping, and others not showing any differences. The present case study showed a significant increase in AST 1 h after the procedure with a subsequent return to control levels after 24 h. On the other hand, ALT displayed a considerable increase after transfer, although this remained below the threshold for significance. Nonetheless, at 24hps, the measured levels of plasmatic ALT significantly decreased compared to the control. Reportedly, prolonged truck transport induces a significant reduction in plasmatic ALT, coupled with a significant increase in AST, following the same patterns as observed in the present case study [47]. ADA has been demonstrated to play an important role in the modulation of inflammatory and homeostatic processes in fish following exposure to stressful events [48,49]. It has been reported that shortly after an acute stress by direct exposure to air, plasmatic levels of ADA display a significant increase, returning to control levels 24hps [50], mimicking the results from the present case study over the same period. Since transfer stress finished after point B, the progressive return of indicators back to control values, as well as the recovery of liver homeostasis was expected.

4.2. Molecular indicators in organs

4.2.1. Gills

Gills are a commonly targeted tissue when investigating the stress response in fish given their degree of exposure to external stressors and their fragility [51]. Given this direct contact with the surrounding environment, it is not surprising that this organ displays the highest degree of variation in terms of expression of relevant stress genes. Three distinct sets of genes (*i.e.* inflammation-related, mucins and endocrine receptors) were investigated in the present case study. The upregulation of *tnfa*, *il1 β* and *hsp70* may indicate the triggering of responses to cellular stress, promoting inflammatory and cell repair processes [52]. It has been suggested that these three genes might display significant upregulations as a response to mechanical stressors, such as handling [52–54]. The results indicate that the potentially pro-inflammatory mechanisms induced by the pumping episode were halted over the course of a week following the stress, therefore suggesting that energetic resources were potentially redirected to cope with the stressor rather than to support inflammatory reaction. Thus, an energy trade-off between stress and immune response-associated resources could apply to this case [55].

In *S. salar*, as in mammals, the expression of mucins-related genes, such as *muc2*, has been described to be stimulated by *tnfa* [11,56], and similar patterns can be observed in the present case study. Mucins can be classified into large secreted gel-forming mucins (*e.g.* *muc2*), and membrane-bound mucins (*e.g.* *muc18*), displaying both shared and distinctive properties, and playing essential roles in determining mucus rheology. Thus, the activation of mucin-coding genes in the gills, particularly the gel-forming type, plays a major role in protecting an organism against pathogens, environmental fluctuations, as well as chemical and physical harm [57,58]. It has been suggested that skin mucus plays an additional major role in inter and intraspecific communication, and in predator avoidance [59], and it is possible that centrifugal pumping might also alter the expression of the relevant genes in this tissue, but this was not investigated in the present case study. Although the mechanisms influencing the expression of mucin-encoding genes in fish are still poorly understood, previous research has shown that branchial *muc2* is significantly upregulated following a handling episode [60], and that *muc18* is significantly upregulated after transfer to sea by pumping [11], as observed during the fish pumping event hereby investigated. Similarly to what was observed with the genes involved in homeostasis and inflammation, the mucin-coding genes investigated here returned to control values 7dps. Overall, it appears as if mucin-coding genes are relevant and suitable for the determination of

stress levels in *S. salar* following centrifugal pumping. The present results show closely related patterns of modulation between the four stress-related genes investigated in the gills (*i.e.* *gr1*, *gr2*, *mr*, and *crf*), agreeing with previous data published on the expression of these in a salmonid species [61].

4.2.2. Head kidney

In the head kidney, the investigated molecular immune and endocrine endpoints display completely different patterns of modulation following the stress when compared to the gills. This is not surprising, given that previous literature has described organ-specific response dynamics to the same stressor [14,62]. In the head kidney, Martorell Ribera et al. [63] reported significant alterations in *il1 β* only 24 h following a direct *in-vitro* insertion of cortisol. In the present case study, the significant downregulation of this gene was only visible at 7dps, although it is possible that it occurred between 1 and 7 days and wasn't detected due to the absence of sampling points during this period. It might also be that, as the present case study is *in-vivo*, the immune-endocrine interaction between cortisol and the head kidney immune cells is delayed compared to an *in-vitro* due to the increased complexity of the matrix and the consequent systemic interrelations. Furthermore, the authors investigated the *in-vivo* impact of a non-virulent injection on the mRNA abundance of *il1 β* in the head-kidney, and described a significant downregulation 72 h post injection [63]. This is potentially more representative of the present results, given the handling and *in-vivo* nature of the experiment. As mentioned above, the present case study did not include a sampling point at 72 h post stress, making the significant decrease in the abundance of this transcript only visible at 7 days, even though it is possible for it to have occurred earlier on. Pelusio et al. [64] has stated that confinement and crowding induces a significant downregulation of *gr1* in the head kidney, as the present results display. This trend has also been observed with different types of stressors, including bacterial infections [64]. This might be explained by *gr*'s expression not being solely influenced by cortisol levels but also depending on immune-endocrine interactions through the stimulation of immune processes. It has also been reported that this gene is often downregulated during exposure to chronic stress, acting as a regulatory mechanism of the stress response [65]. Furthermore, previous studies show that cortisol-dependent modulation differs amongst corticoid receptors (*i.e.* *gr1*, *gr2*, *mr*) in the head kidney of salmonids [61], as reflected by the obtained results. In rainbow trout, it was reported that acute handling and hypoxic stress induced a significant downregulation of *hsp70* in the head kidney, without indications of recovering basal values even 24hps [32]. Furthermore, it appears that, in percids, handling stress regulates the expression of certain genes such as *hsp70* even 144hps, in a clear temperature-dependent manner [66]. Therefore, it cannot be discarded that the mRNA abundance of the genes hereby investigated is still affected by the pumping episode 7dps. At this point, it should be reiterated that the cortisol response observed in the present case study is weak, with low amounts of circulating cortisol. Moreover, not only stress-associated genes are moderately expressed, but responses of the stress-regulatory organs like the head kidney also show low responsiveness. Therefore, this reinforces the idea of the reduced reactivity of the overall HPI axis under the conditions of the investigated RAS in this case study.

The steroidogenic acute regulatory protein (StAR) is responsible for the transport of cholesterol into inner cellular membranes, playing a crucial role in steroidogenesis, and therefore in the onset of the stress response in vertebrates [67]. Expression of *star* has been reported as displaying significant decreases in *S. aurata* head kidney cells following *in-vitro* exposure to ACTH [68]. However, an *in-vivo* experiment performed by the same authors involving netting stress in *S. aurata* resulted in no significant differences in the expression of *star* in the head kidney. It is worth noting that *star* is activated only under high levels of circulating cortisol [69], although other mechanisms are probably at play

when regulating the expression of this gene [68]. It is possible that the fluctuations in mRNA abundance of *star* observed in the present case study are partly modulated by ACTH levels. However, this parameter was not analysed for in the collected samples.

The modulation of the analysed genes clearly follows different patterns in gills and head kidney which might provide further evidence for the occurrence of negative feedback loops or compensatory mechanisms from the central to the peripheral system in order to prevent abrupt dysregulations with potentially strong repercussions on the overall allostatic capacity of the fish. Moreover, having some parameters fail to return to basal values 7 days after the event might hint towards partial recovery, indicating that these fish require a longer period to fully return to homeostasis. However, additional research with increased samples size is required to further investigate these hypotheses. It is also important to note that, given the intricacy and intertwinement of gene function, variations in the expression of single relevant genes does not necessarily translate into functional modifications at the whole-organism level, such as strong immunosuppression or overall performance. Although the observed trends are, to some extent, corroborated by the biochemical analyses in the plasma, the present results should be interpreted as preliminary. Future studies may benefit from a direct comparison of these parameters with functional immune response and long-term performance indicators to confirm the biological relevance of the observed changes in gene expression.

This case study presents both advantages and limitations inherently linked to the industry-based nature of the research. Indeed, being dictated by operational constraints, having a single tank available for transfer resulted in a lack of experimental replicates. Nonetheless, the biological relevance is strengthened by the monitoring of the fish's response over time (*i.e.* regularly from before the stressor to up to a week after the event), enabling for the evaluation of their recovery capacity. Moreover, the Atlantic salmon smolts used in the present case study had been reared for several months under authentic industrial farm conditions, which may have influenced their responses compared to laboratory-reared counterparts. With some parameters being kept confidential, the reproducibility of such studies is often limited, an issue previously highlighted [27]. Nonetheless, this provided the opportunity to investigate a real-life scenario, as opposed to laboratory studies which often lack certain levels of representativeness and realism. More interestingly, this revealed signs of potential HPI-axis exhaustion, possibly linked to this prolonged exposure to RAS, offering a novel perspective for future research and a basis for the development of more humane handling and rearing practices in aquaculture.

5. Conclusions

Overall, the data obtained from the present case study indicate that centrifugal pumping elicited the activation of the primary and secondary stress responses, particularly at the peripheral level, characterised by the rise in circulating cortisol levels and a slightly delayed increase in plasmatic glucose, respectively [13]. This is further corroborated by the upregulation of *gr1*, *gr2*, *mr*, and *crf* in the gills, which are recognised indicators of the generalised stress response in fishes [70]. It also seems as if the investigated event had an impact on the immune status of the fish, inducing inflammation (*i.e.* as evidenced by the upregulation of *tnfa* and *il1β*), and slightly triggered antioxidant defences and cellular repair processes, as well as inducing the significant upregulation of mucin-coding genes.

According to the present data, the fish manage to cope with the transfer and return to control values in most of the investigated parameters around 7 days post stress, indicating that, although the pumping triggered a stress response in the fish, it is likely not maladaptive. Nonetheless, some of the studied endpoints (*e.g.* mRNA abundance of relevant genes in the head kidney and plasmatic ALT) remained significantly altered even 7dps, suggesting that homeostasis was still not attained at this point, and that additional time is required

for the fish to fully recover from the transfer. The allocation of energetic resources to the activation of the primary and secondary stress responses, as well as allostatic processes, might translate into an increased susceptibility of the fish to additional insults [17,18]. Therefore, ensuring stability in the rearing environment during those days might be critical for the prevention of elevated mortality events.

It is important to reiterate that the present case study was conducted in a fully commercial setting and is therefore highly representative of what occurs in a *S. salar* RAS, whereas most of the available literature deals with low-scale, controlled laboratory experiments, mimicking, to the best of their abilities, industrial conditions. It is possible that the prolonged exposure to common stressors in RAS (*e.g.* crowding, sound-scape, constant light) might induce a decrease in responsiveness of the HPI axis and associated inflammatory reactions to subsequent insults, without significantly harming the fish, as, although the response is considerably lower than expected, homeostasis was partly recovered by the end of the experimental period. It is also worth considering that the relatively low increase in circulating cortisol levels hereby observed might translate into a milder immunosuppression, compared to fish which would have displayed a stronger increase.

Further research is necessary to confirm the hypothesis of an impaired HPI-axis, and it would be of great interest to compare fish originating from the same brood being reared in non-recirculating aquaculture settings and in RAS. Moreover, it could prove interesting to follow the same batch of fish throughout the production cycle in a commercial RAS, investigating the response of individuals to each significantly stressful event (*e.g.* during and after each transfer episode) to determine whether it does indeed decrease over time as the fish are repeatedly exposed to additional stressors.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsi.2025.110936>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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